

Detection of Malicious Network Traffic Using Machine Learning

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Abstract Network intrusion detection systems increasingly rely on machine learning to identify malicious activity within large volumes of network traffic. In this project, a flow-based intrusion detection approach is implemented using the UNSW-NB15 dataset. The system operates exclusively on network flow features (e.g., packet counts, byte volumes, flow duration, and behavioral repetition counts) without inspecting packet payloads. A supervised machine learning model was developed in ML.NET (within Visual Studio) using the FastTree gradient-boosted decision tree algorithm. The model was trained on the UNSW-NB15 training set and evaluated on the designated test set. Results: The trained classifier achieved high attack detection rates (recall=98.5%) and an overall accuracy of 87% on unseen data. It detected the majority of attack flows, resulting in only a small false-negative rate (1.5% of attacks missed). However, the precision was lower (82%), indicating some false alarms due to benign traffic being misclassified. These results highlight the strengths of flow-based detection against obvious attacks and its limitations against stealthy or low-volume attacks. The study underscores how flow-level feature characteristics influence detection outcomes and discusses the practical implications of the observed false-positive and false-negative rates. Possible future enhancements include deeper packet inspection and sequential analysis to improve the detection of evasive threats.	Article history Received: 30.3.2026. Revised: 2.5.2026. Accepted: 11.5.2026. Keywords Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Flow-Based Intrusion Detection, Machine Learning, UNSW-NB15 Dataset, ML.NET, FastTree.
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1 Introduction

Modern computer networks generate massive volumes of traffic, making manual analysis and traditional signature and rule-based intrusion detection increasingly difficult [1]. As cyberattacks become more complex, there is a growing need for IDS solutions that can adapt to previously unseen threats. Machine learning and deep learning approaches have therefore received significant attention in intrusion detection research because they can learn complex attack patterns beyond handcrafted rules [2], [3]. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of machine learning for network intrusion detection using flow-level features. Zhang et al. [4] showed that Random Forest classifiers can achieve strong detection performance

on network traffic data, while Kasongo and Sun [5] demonstrated that feature selection combined with gradient boosting significantly improves classification accuracy on the UNSW-NB15 benchmark. Verma and Ranga [3] further highlighted that tree-based ensemble methods are particularly well-suited for IoT network intrusion detection due to their ability to handle non-linear feature interactions without requiring payload inspection.

1.1 Related Work

Machine learning has been widely applied to intrusion detection, particularly using flow-level features that enable scalable monitoring without payload inspection. Classical machine learning approaches, such as Random Forests, have demonstrated strong performance in network intrusion detection tasks [4]. More recent studies on

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the UNSW-NB15 dataset also report competitive results for machine learning-based intrusion detection models, especially when feature selection and tabular classifiers are used [5], [6], [7]. More et al. [6] and Moualla et al. [7] further demonstrated that ensemble and hybrid machine learning approaches can substantially improve detection performance on the UNSW-NB15 dataset when combined with appropriate preprocessing and class balancing strategies. Survey studies further indicate that tree-based and ensemble methods remain attractive because they can capture non-linear feature interactions while retaining a useful degree of interpretability [3]. At the same time, earlier intrusion detection research relied heavily on benchmark datasets such as KDD Cup 99 and NSL-KDD, whose limitations motivated the development of more realistic evaluation datasets [8], [9], [10]. In addition to classical machine learning approaches, recent studies have explored hybrid and deep learning-based intrusion detection systems that combine flow-level features with temporal modeling or payload-aware analysis. While such approaches often improve detection of stealthy attacks, they typically require higher computational resources and reduced interpretability. As a result, flow-based machine learning remains an attractive compromise for scalable intrusion detection, particularly in high-speed or privacy-sensitive environments. Recent survey studies further indicate the effectiveness of machine learning and deep learning techniques for intrusion detection, while also highlighting challenges related to model complexity, interpretability, and deployment in real-world environments [2]. Beyond standard supervised classification, some studies have also explored anomaly-detection and outlier-based approaches for intrusion detection [11].

This paper focuses on a machine learning-based, network-level intrusion detection approach using flow-level traffic data. Network flows summarize communication between endpoints using statistical features such as packet counts, byte volumes, duration, and protocol information, without inspecting packet payloads. While flow-based detection offers scalability and privacy advantages, it relies solely on behavioral patterns to infer malicious

activity. Using the UNSW-NB15 dataset as a benchmark, we evaluate how effectively a machine learning model can detect malicious traffic using only flow features, highlighting both the strengths and limitations of this approach. The objective of this study is not to achieve state-of-the-art performance, but to evaluate a practical, interpretable, and easily deployable flow-based intrusion detection solution using the ML.NET framework. A binary classification model was developed using the FastTree algorithm in ML.NET to distinguish between benign and malicious network flows. The remainder of the paper presents the dataset characteristics, data preprocessing, and model training methodology, evaluation results, analysis of false positives and false negatives, and a discussion of the model's performance and limitations, followed by conclusions and future research directions.

Research contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Implementation and evaluation of a flow-based intrusion detection system on the UNSW-NB15 dataset using the FastTree (GBDT) algorithm within the ML.NET framework.
- A detailed error analysis based on confusion matrix outcomes (FP/FN), including interpretation of which attack behaviors are detected reliably and which remain challenging for flow-based approaches.

2 Problem Definition and Research Challenge

One of the key challenges in modern network intrusion detection systems is identifying malicious traffic without inspecting packet payloads. Due to privacy regulations, widespread encryption, and performance constraints, many practical IDS solutions rely solely on flow-level network data rather than deep packet inspection. Network flows contain only statistical and behavioral features—such as packet counts, byte volumes, flow duration, protocol type, and connection patterns—without revealing packet content. This limitation complicates detection, as many cyberattacks are designed to resemble legitimate traffic or embed malicious intent within packet payloads. Consequently, flow-based IDS

faces a fundamental trade-off: while attacks that produce strong behavioral anomalies can be detected effectively, stealthy or low-volume attacks may evade detection.

This study addresses this challenge by evaluating whether machine learning can distinguish between normal and malicious network traffic using only flow-based features. A supervised learning approach is applied to the UNSW-NB15 dataset, and a FastTree gradient-boosted decision tree model is trained to capture non-linear relationships between flow attributes. The model's effectiveness is assessed using standard evaluation metrics, with particular emphasis on detection rate and the limitations of flow-based intrusion detection. Previous studies and survey papers indicate that flow-based intrusion detection remains challenging for stealthy and low-volume attacks, particularly when payload inspection is unavailable [1], [3].

2.1 Limitations of the Proposed Approach

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, the proposed approach relies exclusively on flow-level features and does not inspect packet payloads or application-layer content. As a result, attacks whose malicious intent is embedded in payload data, encrypted communication, or higher-layer semantics may remain difficult to detect. Second, the model evaluates network flows independently and does not incorporate temporal sequences or long-term contextual information. This limits its ability to detect slow, distributed, or multi-stage attacks whose malicious behavior becomes visible only over time.

Third, although the model achieved high recall, the relatively high false-positive rate may limit its practicality in real-world deployment, where excessive alerts can overwhelm security analysts and increase investigation costs.

Fourth, the evaluation was conducted using a single benchmark dataset, UNSW-NB15, and a single machine learning model, FastTree, implemented in ML.NET. While this supports a focused and interpretable analysis, it limits the generalizability of the findings to other datasets, network environments, and model families. Finally, some attack categories in

the dataset are underrepresented, which may reduce the reliability of detection for rare attacks and increase uncertainty in both false-positive and false-negative outcomes.

3 Dataset

The experiments were conducted using the UNSW-NB15 dataset, a widely used benchmark for network intrusion detection research [12]. The dataset was created by the Cyber Range Lab at UNSW Canberra and combines real benign traffic with synthetically generated contemporary attack behaviors. Network traffic was captured in raw PCAP format and processed using Argus and Bro IDS tools, yielding 49 flow-based features per record, along with class labels [12]. Each record represents a single network flow, described by statistical, temporal, and behavioral attributes, such as packet and byte counts, flow duration, protocol information, and connection-repetition metrics. Importantly, the dataset does not include packet payload data, making it suitable for evaluating purely flow-based intrusion detection approaches. The UNSW-NB15 dataset has been widely used in intrusion detection research. It is generally considered a more realistic benchmark than older datasets such as KDD Cup 99 and NSL-KDD, as it reflects more modern traffic patterns and a broader set of attack scenarios [10], [13]. The dataset contains both benign and malicious traffic, with each flow labeled using a binary class (normal or attack) and, for malicious instances, an associated attack category. UNSW-NB15 defines nine attack categories, including DoS, Exploits, Reconnaissance, Backdoors, and Worms, covering a broad spectrum of attack behaviors. This diversity provides a realistic and challenging evaluation environment compared to older benchmark datasets [12].

A standard train test split provided by the dataset authors was used. The training set consists of 175.341 flows, while the test set contains 82.332 flows collected on different days, enabling evaluation on previously unseen attack instances and supporting realistic generalization assessment [12].

Table 1 Overview of the UNSW-NB15 dataset

Item	Value
Dataset	UNSW-NB15
Total number of records	257673
Training set size	175341
Test set size	82332
Number of original features	49
Number of used features	42
Classification type	Binary (Normal/Attack)
Number of attack categories	9

Table 1 provides a structured overview of the UNSW-NB15 dataset used in this study, summarizing its size, feature composition, and classification characteristics.

UNSW-NB15 was selected due to its modern traffic patterns, diverse attack types, and rich flow-level feature set, making it a suitable foundation for evaluating machine learning-based intrusion detection systems.

4 Methodology

4.1 Data Preparation and Preprocessing

Several preprocessing steps were applied to the UNSW-NB15 dataset before model training. Non-informative or inappropriate attributes were removed, including the id field and the attack_cat label, as the latter would introduce label leakage in a binary classification setting. The service attribute was also excluded to reduce dimensionality and potential bias, since it is sparsely populated and strongly correlated with certain attack types. After basic attribute filtering, each network flow was represented by 42 numerical and categorical features describing traffic statistics and behavioral patterns. It should be noted that this step constitutes simple column removal – the elimination of non-informative or potentially leaking columns – rather than a data-driven feature selection method such as correlation analysis, recursive feature elimination, or dimensionality reduction.

Table 2 Categories of flow-based features used in the model

Feature category	Examples
Traffic volume	sbytes, dbytes, spkts, dpkts
Temporal features	dur, rate
Protocol features	proto, state
Connection repetition	ct_src_ltm, ct_dst_ltm, ct_src_dport_ltm

Table 2 summarizes the main categories of flow-based features used for model training, illustrating how traffic volume, temporal behavior, protocol information, and connection repetition patterns are represented. These feature groups capture complementary aspects of network behavior, allowing the model to effectively discriminate between benign and malicious traffic based on statistical and behavioral deviations.

Categorical attributes, including proto and state, were one-hot encoded to enable their use in the learning process [14]. All remaining features were numerical and used without further transformation. The dataset contained no significant missing values, and any minor missing entries were handled using simple default-value substitution. Feature scaling was not applied, as tree-based models are insensitive to monotonic feature transformations.

4.2 Machine Learning Framework, Procedure, and Implementation

The model was implemented using ML.NET, which provides an integrated pipeline for data preprocessing and model training in a .NET environment. For classification, the FastTree algorithm, a gradient-boosted decision tree method based on the MART framework, was employed [15]. FastTree was selected due to its effectiveness with tabular data, its ability to model non-linear feature interactions, and its strong generalization performance. Its learning principle is consistent with gradient boosting methods widely used for structured data [16], [17]. In intrusion detection research, tree-based and ensemble models have also shown strong performance on network traffic classification tasks [4], [5].

Table 3 FastTree model parameters and implementation details

Parameter	Value
Algorithm	FastTree (GBDT)
Number of trees	359
Learning rate	0.0219
Number of leaves	75
Classification threshold	0.5
Framework	ML.NET
Development environment	Microsoft Visual Studio

Table 3 summarizes the main hyperparameters of the FastTree model and the implementation environment used in this study.

Hyperparameter optimization was performed automatically by the ML.NET AutoML framework within a 1200-second time budget. Rather than applying manual grid search or random search, the AutoML engine employed its internal Bayesian-inspired search strategy to explore combinations of key FastTree hyperparameters, including the number of trees (ranging from 4 to 359 across evaluated trials), the learning rate (ranging from 0.022 to 0.342), the number of leaves per tree (ranging from 4 to 75), the minimum number of examples per leaf, the maximum bin count per feature, and the feature fraction used per split. All configurations were evaluated using an internal 80/20 train/validation split, with MacroAccuracy as the selection criterion. The configuration achieving the highest validation MacroAccuracy (0.9503) used 359 trees, a learning rate of 0.0219, and 75 leaves, resulting in a deeper ensemble with a conservative learning rate, consistent with established gradient boosting best practices. Although a broader search space or a longer time budget might have yielded marginal gains, the selected configuration demonstrated stable and strong performance on the held-out test set, suggesting that the default AutoML boundaries were sufficient for this dataset. The trained model outputs a probability score for each flow, with a threshold of 0.5 used to distinguish between benign and malicious traffic. During the model development phase, multiple supervised classification algorithms available in the ML.NET framework were evaluated.

Table 4 Comparative performance of evaluated models

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
FastTree	87.10%	81.72%	98.63%	89.38%
FastForest	82.18%	75.70%	99.59%	86.02%
SDCA Logistic Regression	55.06%	55.06%	100.00%	71.02%
Linear SVM	55.47%	55.29%	99.97%	71.20%
LBFGS Logistic Regression	70.31%	65.70%	96.42%	78.15%

To justify the selection of the final model, a comparative analysis was conducted using five supervised machine learning algorithms available in ML.NET. All models were trained and evaluated under identical conditions, using the same dataset split and preprocessing pipeline, ensuring a fair comparison. The evaluation was performed using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score metrics.

As shown in Table 4, the FastTree model achieved the best overall performance, particularly in terms of F1-score (89.38%) and a balanced trade-off between precision and recall. Although FastForest achieved slightly higher recall (99.59%), its precision and overall F1-score were lower. The remaining models exhibited significantly lower performance, particularly in precision and accuracy, indicating weaker generalization to this dataset. Based on this comparative analysis, FastTree was selected as the final model for further evaluation.

Model training was performed on the official UNSW-NB15 training set, while evaluation was conducted on the provided test set. Based on the final train test evaluation, no clear signs of substantial overfitting were observed. The trained model was subsequently applied to the test data to generate predictions for performance evaluation. The complete machine learning pipeline was implemented in Microsoft Visual Studio using the ML.NET framework. The solution includes data loading, preprocessing, model training, evaluation, and prediction components. This ensured reproducibility and practical applicability of the proposed approach in a real development environment. The implementation follows a modular pipeline design, enabling reproducibility and

straightforward adaptation to other flow-based intrusion detection datasets. The complete implementation is publicly available as open-source code.

5 Evaluation

We evaluated the trained model on the UNSW-NB15 test set (82332 flows) using standard classification metrics: Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score.

Table 5 Performance metrics on the UNSW-NB15 test set

Metric	Value
Accuracy	87.32%
Precision	82.07%
Recall	98.48%
F1-score	89.53%
False Positive Rate	26.3%
False Negative Rate	1.52%

As shown in Table 5, the model achieves a high detection rate (Recall), indicating effective identification of malicious network flows.

Table 6 Confusion matrix for the FastTree classifier on the UNSW-NB15 test set

	Pred Normal	Pred Attack
Actual Normal	27248	9752
Actual Attack	687	44 645

Figure 1 shows the distribution of benign and malicious flows in the UNSW-NB15 test set, indicating a moderate class imbalance.

Figure 1 Distribution of benign and malicious flows in the UNSW-NB15 test set

Confusion Matrix Analysis: On the test data, the model's predictions can be summarized as follows:

- True Positives (TP)=44645 (malicious flows correctly identified as attacks);
- True Negatives (TN)=27248 (benign flows correctly identified as normal);
- False Positives (FP)=9752 (benign flows incorrectly flagged as attacks, i.e., false alarms);
- False Negatives (FN)=687 (malicious flows missed by the model, incorrectly classified as normal).

These totals correspond to the following performance metrics:

- Accuracy: 87.32%, calculated as $(TP+TN)/(Total\ samples) = (44645+27248)/82332$. This means the model correctly classified about 87% of all flows.
- Precision: 82.07%, defined as $TP/(TP+FP)$. This indicates that, of all flows predicted as malicious, about 82% were truly malicious (18% were false alarms). An 82% precision is relatively good, though it reflects a non-negligible rate of false positives.
- Recall (Detection Rate): 98.48%, defined as $TP/(TP+FN)$. This high recall means the model detected roughly 98.5% of all malicious flows. In other words, it missed only 1.5% of attacks (as false negatives). From a security perspective, high recall is crucial, as false negatives (missed attacks) can be very dangerous. Our model's recall of 98%+ is a positive outcome, indicating it detects nearly all attacks in the test set.
- F1-Score: 89.53%, the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The F1 combines the model's accuracy on positive predictions and its coverage of positive instances. An F1-score of 89.5% reflects well-balanced performance for this imbalanced problem (since the number of normal vs. attack instances is typically unbalanced).

Additionally, we can report the False Positive Rate (FPR) and False Negative Rate (FNR): The FPR was about 26.3% (meaning 26% of actual normal flows

were incorrectly flagged), and the FNR was about 1.52% (meaning only 1.52% of actual attacks were missed). The low FNR is especially important in an IDS context, as missing fewer attacks is often worth tolerating some extra false alerts. However, the relatively high FPR (one in four normal flows triggering an alert) indicates room for improvement in precision or for more conservative tuning. Overall, the evaluation shows that the model is biased towards high recall, successfully catching the vast majority of attacks, at the expense of a higher false alarm rate. This bias can be appropriate for intrusion detection, where missing an attack is typically considered worse than raising a false alarm (which can be investigated by analysts). Next, we analyze the nature of the false positives and false negatives to better understand these results.

6 Analysis of False Negatives and False Positives

The model identifies malicious network traffic by analyzing flow-level features that describe traffic volume, temporal behavior, and connection patterns. Since the selected dataset does not include packet payloads, payload inspection is not possible, and classification decisions rely solely on the statistical and behavioral characteristics of network flows. One group of indicators relates to traffic intensity and flow duration. Attacks that generate abnormal traffic volumes, such as denial-of-service and flooding attacks, are characterized by short or moderate flow durations (dur), elevated byte counts (sbytes, dbytes), and increased transfer rates (rate). In contrast, extremely short flows with minimal data exchange may indicate automated probing or scanning behavior.

Another important set of indicators captures connection repetition and distribution patterns. Features such as ct_src_ltm, ct_dst_ltm, and ct_src_dport_ltm quantify how frequently a source establishes connections to the same destination or to multiple destination ports within a limited time window. High values of these attributes are typical of reconnaissance activities and port-scanning attacks, in which an attacker systematically explores available network services. The model also considers packet-

level statistics and protocol behavior, including the number of packets exchanged (spkts, dpkts), the transport protocol (proto), and the connection state (state). A high number of failed, incomplete, or abnormal connection states increases the likelihood of malicious activity and is often associated with exploit attempts or misconfigured attack tools.

By combining these heterogeneous features, the model learns patterns that deviate from normal benign traffic behavior across multiple attack categories. This enables effective detection of attacks that produce clear statistical or behavioral anomalies, while attacks that deliberately mimic legitimate traffic or rely on payload-level manipulation remain more challenging to identify.

Example of a DoS attack (Denial of Service)

A Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack aims to make a service unavailable to legitimate users by overwhelming the target with an excessive volume of network traffic in a short period, thereby exhausting system or network resources.

Concrete Example from the Dataset (UNSW-NB15, Record 416):

- Duration (dur): 0.417 s
- Source packets (spkts): 10
- Source bytes (sbytes): 13567
- Destination bytes (dbytes): 13854
- Rate: 40.72

This flow shows high data transfer in both directions over a very short period. Large byte counts, short duration, and high transfer rate indicate intense activity targeting the HTTP service, a common DoS target. The model identifies this pattern—short flow, high byte count, and high rate—as typical of a DoS attack. The extreme traffic towards the same service clearly deviates from normal HTTP behavior, correctly classifying the flow as malicious.

By inspecting misclassifications, we gain insight into why the model errs in certain cases, often related to the characteristics of specific attack types and the limitations of flow-based features.

False Negatives (Missed Attacks): The model's false negatives were very limited in number (687 out of

45k attacks), but they exhibit common traits. These missed attacks tended to share a common characteristic: they did not produce strong statistical anomalies in the flow-level features available to the model. Attacks that resemble legitimate traffic patterns, such as low-rate probing or sessions involving only a small number of packets, may generate flows that fall within normal statistical ranges, making them difficult to distinguish from benign traffic based solely on flow features. Similarly, attacks whose malicious intent is primarily embedded in packet content rather than in traffic behavior may not produce sufficient deviations in the available features to trigger correct classification. It should be noted that these observations are based on a general interpretation of the false-negative outcomes and do not constitute a category-level breakdown of missed attack types.

False Positives (Benign flagged as Malicious): The false positives (9752 cases) constituted about a quarter of all actual normal flows, which is substantial. Upon analysis, many false positives were caused by legitimate traffic patterns that momentarily resemble attack behavior. For instance, legitimate high-volume data transfers or bursts - such as software updates, backups, or large file downloads - can generate flows with very high byte counts or packet rates. These can be confused with DoS-like or scanning-like behavior by the model. Also, certain network management or scanning activities (such as vulnerability scans or network mapping performed by administrators) might appear similar to malicious reconnaissance. We observed that flows during busy periods sometimes had elevated ct_* counters (e.g., many connections from a single host in a short period), triggering the model's detection thresholds. In essence, benign traffic outliers that fall in the statistical range of attacks led to false alarms. For example, if a normally quiet host suddenly makes many connections (perhaps due to an automated update checking many servers), the model may flag that as suspicious (thinking it's a port scan). Another factor is that our model was tuned to aggressively detect attacks (favoring recall), which inherently increases FPs. The classification threshold of 0.5 could be adjusted or calibrated to reduce false alerts

at the cost of some missed attacks, depending on operational preferences.

Imbalanced Categories and Errors: It is also worth noting that underrepresented attack categories in the dataset are generally more challenging for the model, as fewer training examples make it harder to learn reliable patterns. This can contribute to both false negatives - where rare attack patterns are not recognized - and false positives - where the model overgeneralizes from limited examples. Class imbalance, therefore, contributes to uncertainty in detection outcomes for less frequent attack types. It should be noted that these observations are based on general reasoning about the effects of class imbalance and do not reflect a category-level breakdown of model errors.

In summary, false negatives predominantly occur for attacks that *hide within normal-like behavior* (slow, stealthy, or requiring payload inspection). In contrast, false positives occur when benign traffic *accidentally exhibits anomalous patterns* (usually high volume or repetition) that are similar to those of attacks. This behavior is a well-known trade-off in flow-based IDS.

7 Discussion

Our results highlight both the strengths and limitations of applying machine learning to flow-based intrusion detection. The proposed model demonstrates strong performance in detecting attacks that generate clear statistical anomalies in flow-level features. Features related to connection repetition and traffic volume, such as ct_dst_ltn , $sbytes$, and $dbytes$, appeared to be particularly informative, helping the model to achieve a high detection rate exceeding 98%. These results suggest that machine learning applied to aggregated flow features is well-suited for detecting volume-based and pattern-based attacks.

However, attacks that resemble legitimate traffic remain challenging for flow-based detection. Attacks whose behavioral characteristics overlap with normal traffic patterns, or whose malicious intent is primarily embedded in packet content, may produce flows with statistically normal characteristics and evade detection. This limitation is inherent to flow-

based IDS, as packet payloads and application-layer semantics are unavailable. Additionally, the model evaluates flows independently, without considering temporal sequences or long-term context, thereby allowing slow, distributed attacks to bypass detection. Incorporating temporal aggregation or sequential analysis could mitigate some of these limitations.

The false-positive rate of 26.3% is a significant practical concern that warrants explicit discussion. In a realistic deployment scenario, this rate means that approximately one in four legitimate network flows would be incorrectly flagged as malicious. For an organization monitoring a high-volume network – for example, processing tens of thousands of flows per hour – this would generate a substantial number of false alerts, placing a considerable burden on security analysts who must investigate each alarm. In environments with limited analyst resources, such a high false alarm rate could reduce the system's operational usability, potentially leading to alert fatigue and missed detections due to analyst overload.

The decision threshold of 0.5 was selected as the default classification boundary provided by the ML.NET framework, which assigns equal cost to false positives and false negatives. This choice reflects a deliberate bias toward maximizing recall – ensuring that as many attacks as possible are detected – at the expense of precision. In security-critical applications where missing an attack is considered more costly than raising a false alarm, this trade-off may be acceptable. However, in operational environments where false alarm management is a priority, the threshold could be increased to reduce the false positive rate, with the understanding that this would also reduce recall. Threshold tuning, therefore, represents a straightforward practical adjustment that could improve the system's usability depending on the specific deployment context. An advantage of the decision tree-based approach is partial interpretability. The model's behavior suggests that features related to repeated connections and abnormal traffic volumes are likely informative, which is consistent with established domain knowledge in flow-based intrusion detection. At the

same time, the model's limitations underscore that detection performance is fundamentally constrained by the information content of flow-level features.

Overall, the results are consistent with prior literature, showing that tree-based and ensemble approaches can achieve strong intrusion detection performance, including in UNSW-NB15-related evaluations, while still facing challenges related to false positives and generalization [3], [4], [5]. While the proposed flow-based approach is effective for many attack types, it should ideally be complemented by additional data sources or detection techniques to address stealthy and content-based threats.

To contextualize the obtained results, Table 7 compares the proposed approach with two relevant studies that evaluated machine learning and deep learning models on the UNSW-NB15 dataset for binary intrusion detection.

Table 7 Comparison of the proposed approach with related studies on the UNSW-NB15 dataset

Study	Approach	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Waghmode et al. (2025)	LS-SVM + exhaustive feature selection	93.30 %	100%	98%	~99%
Jouhari et al. (2024)	CNN-BiLSTM + χ^2 feature selection, 20 features	97.90 %	97.91 %	97.90 %	97.90 %
This work	FastTree GBDT, 42 features, ML.NET	87.32 %	82.07 %	98.48 %	89.53 %

Waghmode et al. [18] proposed a quantum-inspired least-squares support vector machine (LS-SVM) combined with exhaustive feature selection, achieving 93.30% accuracy with near-perfect precision and recall on the UNSW-NB15 dataset. Jouhari et al. [19] developed a lightweight CNN-BiLSTM hybrid model using Chi-square feature selection to reduce the feature set to 20 features, achieving an accuracy of 97.90%, precision of 97.91%, recall of 97.90%, and F1-score of 97.90% in binary classification.

The proposed approach achieves a lower overall accuracy (87.32%) than either reference study. However, this is expected given the methodological differences. The proposed approach applies only basic attribute filtering and does not employ a data-driven feature selection method. In contrast, both reference studies apply systematic feature selection techniques - exhaustive search in the case of Waghmode et al. and Chi-square selection in the case of Jouhari et al. - which likely contribute to their higher accuracy. The most distinctive strength of the proposed approach is its recall of 98.48%, which exceeds the recalls reported by both reference studies (98% and 97.90%, respectively), indicating that the FastTree model is highly effective at capturing attack flows. The trade-off is a higher false positive rate, reflecting the model's bias toward detection sensitivity over precision, which is a deliberate characteristic well-suited to security-critical applications where missing an attack is more costly than raising a false alarm.

8 Conclusion

This paper presented a machine learning-based approach for detecting malicious network traffic using the flow-based UNSW-NB15 dataset. A FastTree gradient-boosted decision tree model implemented in ML.NET was used to classify network flows as benign or malicious. The results demonstrate that with appropriate preprocessing and basic attribute filtering, flow-based intrusion detection systems can effectively identify attacks that produce clear behavioral anomalies, such as flooding and scanning.

At the same time, the study highlights inherent limitations of relying solely on flow-level features. Stealthy attacks that closely resemble legitimate traffic, as well as attacks whose malicious intent is embedded in encrypted or application-layer content, may evade detection. The observed false positives further illustrate the difficulty of distinguishing malicious and benign outliers when only limited statistical information is available. These findings indicate that flow-based machine learning approaches should be considered as one component of a broader, multi-layered security strategy. Based on analyses of model errors and practical deployment

considerations, this study further discusses the strengths and limitations of flow-based machine learning for intrusion detection. It provides recommendations to improve real-world usability, including threshold tuning, sequential analysis, and hybrid detection strategies.

Several directions for future work can enhance detection capabilities. Integrating deep packet inspection with flow analysis could enable the detection of content-based attacks that are invisible in flow summaries. Incorporating temporal or sequence-based analysis would enable modeling of attack progression over time, thereby improving the detection of slow, distributed attacks. Additional feature sources, such as host-based data or unsupervised anomaly detection, may further reduce false negatives and false alarms.

In conclusion, this work shows that machine learning, and gradient-boosted tree models in particular, can provide effective intrusion detection using flow-level data. Addressing the identified limitations through hybrid and context-aware approaches represents a promising direction for improving the robustness of future intrusion detection systems.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) report there are no competing interests to declare;

Data availability statements: The source code and implementation associated with this study are publicly available at: <https://github.com/ivanastojic/DetekcijaZlonamjernogMreznogPrometa>

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